

6: Sharing Research Data and Infrastructure to Study Proteins

A research group's impact on the study of circular dichroism

With over **375,000 analyses run**, the **DICHROWEB** online analysis tool is a clear example of how data interoperability can enhance research. Before the tool was released, researchers in the field of biology needing to study protein structures had to deal with a range of different programs using a variety of inputs and outputs that were not compatible with one another. Consequently, even though those programs were publicly available, it was very difficult to use them interchangeably. Bonnie Ann Wallace (Professor of Molecular Biophysics at the Birbeck College, University of London) and her team developed DICHROWEB as a web-based tool allowing the use of many algorithms to analyse circular dichroism (CD) and synchrotron radiation (SRCD) spectroscopy data.

The DICHROWEB server and the Protein Circular Dichroism Data Bank

The DICHROWEB tool accepts any recognised data format in the field and allows access to the **Protein Circular Dichroism Data Bank (PCDDDB)**, a repository on the topic. The PCDDDB was also created by Prof Wallace, in collaboration with Dr Bob Janes from Queen Mary University of London. The PCDDDB is a publicly available repository for CD and SRCD data to enable sharing, dissemination, and re-use in the field. DICHROWEB and the PCDDDB are linked, so that users of the PCDDDB can run their own computational analyses on the data deposited. This improves the research workflow, as a direct

connection between the repository and the analysis tools means that users are not required to download or import/export data.

Prof. Wallace and her team implemented a large number of functions in the DICHROWEB portal, both novel and from the literature. These take into account advances in X-ray crystallography, NMR spectroscopy, and bioinformatics, thus, exploiting existing knowledge and building on it to uncover new methods and findings.

How DICHROWEB and the PCDDDB are helping researchers

DICHROWEB and the PCDDDB are being used by both academic researchers (for scientific investigations and teaching) and industrial stakeholders. DICHROWEB has over 3,600 registered users and the tool gathered over 1,000 academic citations, while the PCDDDB received 175,000 unique hits from 41 different countries.

Among the **industrial users** of the platforms, there are companies in the pharmaceutical, biotechnology, and food sectors, ranging from multinational firms to SMEs. In addition, biomedical product and clinical diagnostics suppliers are among the users of the PCDDDB. These commercial players successfully exploited DICHROWEB and the PCDDDB, developing analyses of the stability and solution properties of proteins and filing 11 patent applications citing the research group's papers (patent holders include Roche Holding AG, Pfizer Inc. and Colpliant Ltd). The importance of Prof Wallace and her team's efforts have been widely

recognised and their work has been presented at several international conferences.

The resources are widely used in teaching both in the UK and internationally, including workshops for researchers ([summer school](#)) and University courses.

Title	6: Sharing Research Data and Infrastructure to Study Proteins
Subtitle	A research group's impact on the study of circular dichroism
Abstract	The DICHROWEB and PCDDDB platforms are widely used for the study of proteins. Since their release, hundreds of thousands of users accessed them, from both academia and the private sector. In academia, the platforms fuel research and teaching, while they led to several advances in industry, including the development of 11 patents.
Keywords	protein; repository; infrastructure
Research subject area	MEDICAL AND HEALTH SCIENCES
Type of RDM impact/benefit	Reproducibility; Efficiency in research and data re-use (e.g., reduce duplication of effort); Socio/Economic impact; Methodological impact (e.g., new approaches developed)
Summary Impact Type	Impact on health and wellbeing
Facts and figures	375,000 analyses 3,600 registered users over 1,000 citations
Original dataset from which the impact arose	
Maturity of the initiative/data source	Long-standing (5+ years)
Year (e.g., first data release, first output, year of impact)	2001
Organisations involved	Birkbeck College
Academic citations	<p>Lobley A., Whitmore L. & Wallace B.A. (2002). [DICHROWEB: an interactive website for the analysis of protein secondary structure from circular dichroism spectra](http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/18.1.211). <i>Bioinformatics</i>.</p> <p>Whitmore L. & Wallace B.A. (2004). [DICHROWEB, an online server for protein secondary structure analyses from circular dichroism spectroscopic data](http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkh371). <i>Nucleic Acids Res</i></p> <p>Lees J.G., Miles A.J., Wien F. & Wallace B.A. (2006). [A reference database for circular dichroism spectroscopy covering fold and secondary structure space](http://people.cryst.bbk.ac.uk/~ubcg25a/BI_reprint.pdf). <i>Bioinformatics</i>.</p> <p>Whitmore L. & Wallace B.A. (2008). [Protein secondary structure analyses from circular dichroism spectroscopy: methods and reference databases](http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/bip.20853). <i>Biopolymers</i>.</p> <p>Wallace B.A. & Janes R.W. (2010). [Synchrotron radiation circular dichroism (SRCD) spectroscopy: an enhanced method for examining protein conformations and protein interactions](http://dx.doi.org/10.1042/BST0380861). <i>Biochem Soc Trans</i>.</p> <p>Whitmore L., Woollett B., Miles A.J., Janes R.W. & Wallace B.A. (2010). [The protein circular dichroism data bank, a Web-based site for access to circular dichroism spectroscopic data](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.str.2010.08.008). <i>Structure</i>.</p>

	Whitmore L., Woollett B., Miles A.J., Klose D.P., Janes R.W. & Wallace B.A. (2011). [PCDDDB: the Protein Circular Dichroism Data Bank, a repository for circular dichroism spectral and metadata](http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkq1026). Nucleic Acids Res.
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